

Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain Review

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GAME INFO

- **ORIGINAL TITLE:** Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain —メタルギアソリッドV ザ・ファントム・ペイン—
- **DIRECTOR:** Hideo Kojima
- **PRODUCER:** Hideo Kojima
- **DEVELOPER:** Kojima Productions
- **PUBLISHER:** Konami Holdings Corporation
- **GENRE:** Action-adventure/stealth
- **PLATFORMS:** PlayStation 3, PlayStation 4, Xbox 360, Xbox One, Microsoft Windows
- **RELEASE DATE:** 1-09-2015 —2-09-2015 in Japan—
- **PRICE:** \$59.99 / £59.99 — PlayStation 4, Xbox One, and Microsoft Windows; \$49.99 / £49.99 — PlayStation 3 and Xbox 360 — retail launch prices—

Official cover of the international version of the video game *Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain*

Hideo Kojima Did It Again

Kojima and his team reunited one last time to work at Konami before leaving the company, delivering the final numbered official entry of the espionage, action, and science fiction Metal Gear saga with *Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain*.

I could not define my feelings any better than the subtitle I placed above, after completing the secret mission that reveals the true ending of the game, following the credits and the post-credits scene, so typical of the Japanese creator; the extra sequences; and playing the online mode, raiding enemy bases, and defending my own for over a year...

Rest assured, I will not reveal any vital plot points, so as not to ruin the experience, which is highly recommended to experience firsthand.

Even though I do not give this game a perfect final score, it does not mean it does not deserve the label of “genre masterpiece” from players and critics alike, as the drawbacks and issues it suffers largely stem from its troubled development, and do not overshadow all the incredible positives it brings.

Gameplay Mechanics

In this game, the development team has managed to surpass how a stealth title is played like no one has since the first *Metal Gear* on the MSX—the first game in the genre ever.

The controls have been perfected, with an immediate, intuitive, and truly magnificent response whether using a controller or keyboard and mouse; the gameplay mechanics, scenarios, equipment, and freedom to choose how to approach the protagonist’s mission objectives have all been improved.

This is very similar to the early Hitman series, a great success, allowing *The Phantom Pain* to become not just Kojima Productions’ story—a team already expelled from Konami when this game was launched—but the player’s unique experience in navigating its development. This is noticeable throughout the game.

Stealth will always be the optimal approach for successfully completing our missions and for our soldiers to live to tell the tale.

Calling this a sandbox game might not be entirely accurate, as Kojima and his team did not aim to make it a true open-world game, but rather a series of enemy bases and camps to assault, all spread across a large map, giving us freedom in choosing which missions to undertake and in what order.

In this *Metal Gear*, we can complete missions in more ways than ever before, even changing our approach mid-mission due to a mistake or for fun, and still succeed. For example, infiltrating an enemy base in complete stealth, but one guard discovers us after we accidentally break a bottle...

We then call XO Miller, our second-in-command, to send a rocket launcher via helicopter, creating an *Apocalypse Now*-worthy spectacle in the enemy base; leaving nothing standing and completing the mission after leaving the area.

Or we simply hide, lure enemies to a specific area, take them out... or wait for the “storm” to pass, or for a timely sandstorm to help us sneak into the enemy’s den more easily by obstructing their vision. Possibilities seem to be almost endless for the player, and this speaks a lot of this game, in such a positive way.

This is a completely new experience in a *Metal Gear*, giving a great sense of “I messed up, but life goes on,” completely unprecedented in the saga.

The adaptive difficulty and AI response to our actions, preparing for our infiltrations based on how previous missions were handled, further accentuate this, introducing new threats.

If we headshot soldiers or tranquillise them, they will equip helmets in future encounters to prevent us from repeating the same tactic too easily; guard shifts occur in real time, and suddenly a truck with soldiers may approach, catching the player off-guard.

Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain has been harshly criticised by the most devoted followers of the Metal Gear franchise—who, in reality, only demand innovation but rarely accept it when delivered, preferring “more of the same with a bit of new”—yet it remains the best stealth video game in history and the best-playable Metal Gear, though years away from the memorability of other entries in terms of story and character charisma or boss fights.

One negative aspect is the inclusion of microtransactions, which, while optional, accelerate progress for players who purchase certain content—somewhat excessive for a non-free game. Fortunately, they are unnecessary to complete the story or develop Mother Base, and can be entirely avoided if desired. Several paid DLCs—outfits and weapons—are also included.

There are two distinct online modes. The first involves infiltrating other players’ bases to eliminate or kidnap guards, adding them to your army, and stealing resources—a lot of fun, especially when player revenge is involved. Not killing enemy soldiers allows recruiting them for your base.

Big Boss patrolling Mother Base, waiting for any player to infiltrate and swipe those nice resource containers.

Both enemy and player bases are alerted when an infiltration occurs, allowing real-time control of soldiers—or Snake himself—to defend Mother Base.

Additionally, it is possible not to develop nuclear weapons, unlocking an extra sequence or ending if no player possesses them—extremely hard to achieve due to the online community’s unpredictable behaviour.

The second online mode is *Metal Gear Online*, a dedicated shooting mode launched as an add-on, included with the base game, where players face off with customizable avatars and Metal Gear franchise characters.

Presentation and Atmosphere

To say the performance of the Fox Engine is wonderful is an understatement. The game looks simply spectacular for its time, regardless of the platform—Xbox 360 and PlayStation 3 versions, being from the previous generation, look only slightly worse than the later-gen counterparts —PS4 and Xbox One— at the time of this review.

Optimization across all platforms is superb. On PC —Windows and Steam—, it is possible to reach a constant 60 FPS—or more—while playing in true 4K resolution, not just upscaled. All of this is achievable without overly demanding hardware, with the major drawbacks being related to popping —also noticeable in the console versions—.

The cinematic sequences, contrary to some claims, are not that scarce, and they are also fully rendered with the game engine in real time.

In terms of sound, Kojima Productions’ work is impeccable. Every sound feels accurate and spectacular, recreating the atmosphere of Afghanistan and the Angola-Zaire border, fully immersing the player.

The soundtrack, however, is hit or miss. Harry Gregson-Williams produces it, but does not compose it fully—Norihiro Hibino or many regular series members are also absent. It serves as accompaniment rather than standing out like previous Metal Gear soundtracks. Some tracks shine, though, like Quiet’s Theme, performed by Stephanie Joosten, who voices and embodies the character.

Where the game truly shines musically is its use of 1970s and 1980s classics, integrated into the setting. Kojima incorporated the Walkman, available at the time, allowing Snake—and the player—to use it, even adding custom music in the PC version.

A True “Phantom Pain”

Due to its unfinished nature—primarily because of Kojima and his team’s expulsion from Konami—the game leaves some story gaps unresolved, giving a sense of “phantom pain.”

Ishmael, addressing the player

The story is a homage to Herman Melville’s *Moby Dick*, with Kojima’s Moby Dick Studios, Joakim Mogren, and other meta references. It also nods to *Kagemusha: The Shadow of the Warrior* —1980— by Akira Kurosawa. Many references remain deliberately vague in this article to avoid spoilers, though fans correctly speculated based on early trailers.

The plot continues after Snake’s original Mother Base is attacked, with Snake hospitalized in Cyprus to hide from enemies. Awakening from a coma, he meets Ishmael, who calls us “Ahab.” Just as Captain Ahab lost a leg, Big Boss lost an arm, —Miller lost an arm and a leg and suffered eye damage—.

Ishmael guides Ahab, leading Big Boss into a spiral of hate and revenge, questioning identities and motivations, and making us feel that there's no hope: just retaliation. Vengeance drives the adventure: against Cipher, XOF, and Major Zero. The protagonist and his comrades are consumed by retaliatory desires, mirroring the original *Moby Dick* crew. The story's gray, tragic tone has caused some criticism, but it is clearly intentional—far from Hollywood-epic climaxes.

Character development is compelling. Take Kazuhira Miller as an example: as he shifts from affable to weary; Kazuhira becomes the most nuanced character, even surpassing Big Boss/Naked Snake in player connection. Kojima's narrative surprises, twists, and open-ended questions exemplify his signature style.

Big Boss and Ishmael hide from their enemies in one of the most intense and emotional prologue scenes of the series. It already foreshadows what awaits us: a very mature, highly visceral Metal Gear that treats the player as an adult, with all the joys and disappointments that entails at every turn.

Storytelling and Gameplay Integration

The story starts slowly post-prologue due to shortened cutscenes but gains intensity in key scenes. During this said prologue, Big Boss and Ishmael hide from enemies in one of the hardest and most emotional introduction sequences. The game treats players as adults, balancing joy and disappointment, and this shows since the first minutes of gameplay.

Unlike early Metal Gear titles, the narrative is more episodic, akin to a TV series, with mid-shots, sequence shots and other techniques typical of the medium. Fewer cinematics exist, yet each is meticulously crafted, some outstanding.

Audio tapes supplement story details; however, the slow reveal and mission repetition dilute narrative impact. Extended gameplay length affects emotional resonance, making progress feel slower—similar to *Red Dead Redemption*, though less well-paced. The cassette recordings are detailed and believable, enhancing immersion.

Characters

Kojima Productions excels at crafting memorable one-off characters, like Quiet or Skull Face, with special mentions for Code Talker—a Diné/Navajo scientist—and returning figures from *Peace Walker*. Some embody 1980s TV clichés as homage.

Snake and Ocelot with D-Dog at Mother Base, the haven of the Diamond Dogs, Snake's new army

Skull Face, revealed in *Ground Zeroes*, finally has his motivations fully explored in *The Phantom Pain*. Voice performances, such as James Horan—Skull Face—and Kiefer Sutherland—Big Boss—or Akio Ōtsuka—Big Boss in the Japanese version—, elevate character engagement. Diamond Dog—D-Dog—is a fully realized canine companion.

The “buddy” system adds mission diversity. D-Horse provides rapid movement and mobile cover; D-Dog aids stealth—although he can also help you in a more aggressive approach—; Quiet can eliminate or tranquillise enemies, and can be used to wreak havoc on enemy lines as a distraction, while we infiltrate; D-Walker functions as robotic transport and combat support. By the way, Quiet evolves into a charismatic character, developing a respectful bond with Snake reminiscent of his relationship with The Boss.

Kojima's Farewell to Metal Gear

Big Boss and Quiet, a deadly duo in combat. They develop a strong bond of camaraderie and friendship. As we can see, Quiet is far from being just a ‘doll’ or an object of desire in this adventure, even though her appearance remains overly revealing, provocative and sexualised.

The game positions players as agents within the story. Strengthening bonds with characters unlocks plot points and gear. Mother Base itself grows alongside Big Boss, “physically” reflecting recruitment and progress.

Kojima's farewell is experiential: players “are” Big Boss throughout. Moments echo Snake's interactions with The Boss in *MGS3*, emphasising player agency. The true ending reinforces consequences, blending disgust and triumph. Players witness Big Boss confronting morally weighty decisions, experiencing both responsibility and disappointment. The game makes **you**

understand that you are the person who pulls the trigger when Snake faces a relevant choice.

The ending ties Big Boss' story to the original MSX/NES *Metal Gear*, despite content cuts and repetitive missions. Kojima delivers the “phantom pain” narrative unconventionally, eschewing epic finales for subtle, reflective closure. This became even more evident once Kojima's departure from Konami took place, as the Metal Gear franchise became an orphan.

Scores

- **Overall:** 91/100
- **Story:** 85/100
- **Graphics:** 100/100
- **Sound :** 90/100
- **Originality:** 80/100
- **Gameplay:** 100/100
- **Review Title:** Must-Play

Conclusions

Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain is essential for action-stealth fans and offers a different experience for those tired of classic action games. While not delivering the franchise's ultimate story closure, it stands as a stealth genre masterpiece. Its 1980s homage, technical and artistic polish, and broad platform availability make it highly accessible.

Big Boss/Venom Snake alongside Quiet in my game

Sources

- **Text:** *Metal Gear Solid V – The Phantom Pain* official website | **Article by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
- **Images:** Personal captures of *Metal Gear Solid V – The Phantom Pain* —PC/Steam version

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